

Academic Leadership and Professional Skills among the Teachers in Higher Education Institutions

¹ I. BENJAMIN PRABAHAR & ² Dr. V. BASTIN JEROME

¹ Research Scholar (Full Time), Department of Commerce, St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli.

Email.ID : Benjaminprabahar.vip@gmail.com

² Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli.

Email.ID : bastinjerome@gmail.com

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Abstract: Academic leadership in higher education institutions is that they make decisions and to do quickly how to manage big educational societies, lecturing students', educators', and employees' requirements, and society's desires. This study highlights the main experiments encountered by academic leaders and appreciates their rejoinders. The current study purposes to examine the insights and practices of academic leaders and professional skills in their respective fields. Professional skills state to switch information technology (IT) and additional areas such as computer operation, the establishment of online databases, searching for information through the Internet and designing websites. By using a simple random sampling technique, the researcher collected data from 132 teachers who are working in a college in Theni District. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents and asked to fill out it. With the help of statistical analysis, the researcher concluded. The finding of the study is confirming the unity of the main mechanisms of educational and construction processes is probable only on an appreciated basis of individualization.

Key Words: Academic Leadership, Professional Skills, Ability of College Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions are social places, and educating and learning is a social cycle. Under studies learn as a team with educators, in the organization of their peers, with family backup, and in an accommodative school climate (Kyamanywa & Redding, 2021). Instruction frets about the advancement of a singular's erudite person, physical, innovative, social, profound, and otherworldly aspects (Evans, 2018). Organizations of instruction ought to be a sustaining ground for the inside and out comprehensive improvement of an understudy. The motivation behind life is step by step unfurled to an understudy through the course of training, and such indispensable methodology can be named comprehensive schooling (Dumulescu & Muşiu, 2021). The improvement of individual, relational, and cultural juvenile capabilities is essential for positive versatile results.

The current review embraces an uplifting perspective towards juvenile improvement in the principal year of school or the College and holds that abilities can be upgraded through orderly intercessions and headings (Su & Wang, 2022). This part presents a broad comprehension of all-encompassing instruction, puberty, social and profound learning, and positive youth improvement (Celik, 2017). The current review expects that initiative can be

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created through train what's more, insight. The administration abilities investigated in this study incorporate nine abilities as made sense by Karnes and Chauvin (2005). The nine abilities are as per the following: Fundamentals of leadership, Speech Communication skills, decision-making skills, written communication skills, group dynamic skills, character-building skills, personal skills, problem-solving skills, and planning skills. The expert abilities for dialects incorporate a significant number of those generally recorded under scholastic abilities (which can be moved to a wide range of occupations), profession the board - ordinarily created by dialects divisions in a coordinated effort.

Regarding subject explicit scholastic abilities, all establishments give impressive consideration to the improvement of the language abilities referenced somewhere else in this aide, both inside center/obligatory courses (or modules) and as isolated discrete courses (Anufrieva, 2022). It is vital for all language teachers associated with similar understudies to examine evaluation gives together, to rehearse consistency no matter how you look at it. Understudies rush to recognize irregularities in educating, learning, and appraisal practice and they are turning out to be increasingly quarrelsome (Zueva, 2019). Strong appraisal practice, cooperative staff advancement, and cross-dialects staff-understudy discourse are indispensable for the powerful execution (A. Black, 2015).

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the leadership quality among the college teachers
2. To determine the professional skills of the college teachers
3. To explore the relationship between academic leadership and professional skills among teachers in higher education institutions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shroff (2012) framed that the fundamental target of fundamental ability training is to empower understudies to foster an idea of oneself as a commendable and contributing individual from the general public. Other than procuring information, understudies ought to have interactive abilities, close-to-home equilibrium, time usage abilities, monetary education, wellbeing cognizance, and critical thinking abilities among others. To guarantee an individual's all-encompassing turn of events, character building and worth based instructing is another fundamental thing.

Tatlah and Iqbal (2012) concentrated on the administration style of optional school pioneers concerning school adequacy. The review was directed at the example of 300 school heads of the Punjab territory of Pakistan. The consequences of the review uncover a measurably critical connection between initiative styles and the viability of the schools.

Luft (2012) deliberate the transformational leadership method and associated the leadership style. The researcher considered the connection of transformational leadership with efficacy and school climate. This study was accompanied by 749 students with 45 teachers from two different schools. The results reveal that the transformational leadership style has a positive influence on the efficacy of the teacher and school climate.

Ezeani Squeeze and Ugwu (2015) explored the latest things, requirements, and chances of amazing skills in Librarianship in Nigeria. The principal objective of the review was to look at the degree of amazing skill in librarianship and to determine the ongoing status, patterns, and open doors among the scholarly Bookkeepers in Nigeria. For the review, five inquiries were figured out to know librarianship as a calling, to evoke the endeavors made by curators considering the proficient turn of events, to decide on strategies for getting new skills, and to recognize the job of expert bodies in advancing amazing skill and greatness.

Johnston and Williams (2015) directed a concentrate on, "Abilities and information need evaluation of current and future Library experts in Qatar". The review centered on five classifications like segment information; instructive status; work data; proficient abilities and expert turn of events. The review members were Library experts, LIS Understudies, and library directors in Qatar. The review depended on the Nexus Evaluation study which was directed in Australia.

Day and Sammons (2016) led a survey concentrating on the fruitful administration in schools which included segments of characterizing authority; audit of different viable models of administration; discoveries of significant explore that have made huge commitments in initiative; evaluating global viewpoints broadly utilized for research in administration; values, morals and ethics expected for productive administration; a mix of different types of effective administration approaches; and characterizing ground-breaking, educational, and conveyed authority draws near.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted with college teachers by using a simple random sampling technique. By using this method, the researcher collects 132 responses from the samples in Theni District. The structured questionnaire was distributed to gather the response from the targeted respondents. To analyze the collected responses, some statistical tools were used namely, percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA test, and correlation analysis. In this study, the reliability of the variables in academic leadership is 0.893 and professional skills is 0.915. It represents that the variables are more reliable and suggested for further research.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no association between gender and academic leadership of college teachers.
- There is no relationship between the age category and the professional skills of college teachers.
- There is no correlation between academic leadership and the professional skills of college teachers.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table – 01: Frequency Distribution

Variables		No. of Respondents	%
Gender	Male	64	48.48
	Female	68	51.52
Age	Less than 25	53	40.15
	26 – 35	21	15.91
	36 – 45	35	26.52
	More than 46	22	16.67
Monthly Income	Less than 25000	30	22.72
	25001 – 50000	53	40.15
	50001 – 75000	35	26.52
	More than 75001	14	10.61
Experience	Less than 5 yrs	49	37.12
	6 – 10 yrs	24	18.18
	11- 15 yrs	21	15.91
	More than 16 yrs	23	17.42
N = 132			

Source: Primary Data

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From the above table - 01, 64 (48.48 per cent) respondents were male and 68 (51.52 per cent) respondents were female. 53 (40.15 per cent) respondents belong to less than 25 years old, 21 (15.91 per cent) respondents belong to 26 - 35 years old, 35 (26.52 per cent) respondents belong to 36 - 45 years old, and 22 (16.67 per cent) respondents belong more than 46 years old. 30 (22.72 per cent) respondents have less than 25000 as monthly income, 53 (40.15 per cent) respondents have 25001 - 50000 as monthly income, 35 (26.52 per cent) respondents have 50001 - 75000 as monthly income, and 35 (26.52 per cent) respondents have 75001 as monthly income. 49 (37.12 per cent) respondents have less than 5 years of experience, 24 (18.18 per cent) respondents have 6 - 10 years of experience, 21 (15.91 per cent) respondents have 11 - 15 years of experience, and 23 (17.42 per cent) respondents have more than 16 years of experiences.

Table - 02: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender	132	1.00	2.00	3.216	1.138
Age	132	1.00	3.00	3.250	1.224
Monthly Income	132	1.00	2.00	2.704	0.720
Experience	132	1.00	4.50	2.762	0.793
Academic Leadership	132	2.00	5.00	3.300	0.931
Professional Skills	132	1.00	2.00	3.012	0.915

Source: Primary Data

From the above table - 02, the descriptive statistics showed that the mean score for gender is 3.216 with a standard deviation of 1.138, the mean score for age is 3.250 with a standard deviation of 1.224, and the mean score for monthly income is 2.704 with a standard deviation of 0.720, the mean score of experience is 2.762 with a standard deviation of 0.793, the mean score of academic leadership is 3.300 with a standard deviation of 0.931, and the mean score of professional skills is 3.012 with a standard deviation of 0.915.

Table - 03: One-way ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	286.16	18.00	15.90	8.47	0.00	1.61
Within Groups	11334.10	6042.00	1.88			
Total	11620.26	6060.00				

Source: Primary Data

From the above table - 03, the actual *p*-value (0.00) is less than the significance value (0.05), and simultaneously the *f* value (8.47) is greater than the *f* critical (1.61). So, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis was accepted in this study.

Table – 04: Karl-Pearson Correlation

	Academic Leadership	Professional Skills
Academic Leadership	1.000	0.894**
Professional Skills	0.894**	1.000

(** represents a significance level of 0.01)

From table – 04, the correlation value of academic leadership and professional skills is 0.894. The association was significant at 1% or 0.01. It showed that there is a positive relationship between academic leadership and professional skills among college teachers. So, the null hypothesis (H₃) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Table – 05: Result of Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Null	Alternate
There is no association between gender and academic leadership of college teachers.	-	<i>Accepted</i>
There is no relationship between the age category and the professional skills of college teachers.	-	<i>Accepted</i>
There is no correlation between academic leadership and the professional skills of college teachers.	-	<i>Accepted</i>

SUGGESTION

In present-day culture, the famous and serious master is the proficient having specific well-developed communicative and authoritative abilities. Development of delicate abilities is one of the instructive patterns and obligatory factors which permit one to find out available competencies of the specialists all the more beneficially. Today there is a requirement for the training change taking into account calls of the computerized world and new technological transformation for the delicate skills development. In a rapidly changing world, the acknowledgment of the educational circumstances for the individualization of the instructive interaction focused on the development of administration abilities can satisfactorily meet the prerequisites of current creation, science, and society; structure fundamental abilities for a fruitful life and expert worth self-assurance of future experts in college framework.

CONCLUSION

Our designs related to scholarly opportunity have empowered us to settle various issues related to mankind; nonetheless, those arrangements might have included some significant pitfalls as far as current real factors. Without question incivility and eventually harassing ways of behaving have expanded, which adversely influence the improvement of connections and cooperative tries important to take care of the horde of issues confronting this present reality. Advanced education is a business, what's more, we can't keep on moving toward our difficulties from a transient viewpoint. We should take an all more long-haul approach while taking care of the difficulties we are right now confronting. Advanced education is in a dubious position. On the off chance that we try not to develop such that tends to our difficulties and potentially open doors, we risk turning into a remnant

of the past. The specialized college's understudies need to foster proficient administration delicate abilities and communication in the exceptionally cut throat and greetings tech climate in the states of worldwide meta patterns, digitalization of all life circles, mechanization and robotization, globalization (monetary, mechanical, and social), segment changes, development of organized society, the organization advancements and choices in light of the blockchain innovations. The results displayed that the gender category highly influenced the academic leadership among college teachers, male teachers highly occupied the leading positions rather than females. The age category impacts the professional skills of the teachers. Because the high professionals are having rich experiences and expertized knowledge which is comparatively lesser than the fresher. So, there is a connection between academic leadership and the professional skills of teachers in colleges.

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